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Exploring transmedia storytelling through original songs in award-winning Spanish films

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Abstract

Popular music in cinema has been analysed from a range of perspectives that consider the music's function, its meaning, the articulation of discourses, identity representation and nostalgia. However, there is scant academic literature that applies a transmedia perspective to analyse how original songs created for a motion picture expand on the film's storytelling. With the aim of contributing to and furthering research into transmedia storytelling and popular music, a sample set of songs that won a Goya award in the second decade of the 21st century is analysed to assess their capacity to enrich the storytelling of each film. In general terms, the lyrics of songs, music videos, lyric videos¹ and videos shared by users on TikTok are observed to spread the film's storytelling by reinforcing the main premise and creating a series of intertexts. A double promotional function is also observed, namely that the films act as a platform for famous artists to disseminate their work, reaching new audiences, while the original songs help to promote the films, not only through the songs themselves, but also

through promotional music videos that emphasise some of the storytelling aspects of the films.

Introduction

Since 1986, the Academy of Cinematographic Arts and Sciences of Spain (hereinafter, the Academy) has issued awards, known as Goyas, to the best professionals from the various technical and creative specialities that are involved in a film's production. However, the category for original songs was only established by the Spanish Academy in 2001, almost 70 years later than the Oscars, which have included an award for this music category since 1934².

The Goya award for best original song was introduced at a time when the cinema and music industries were undergoing a crisis brought about by the shift from an analogue to a digital model. This period of digital transition in the cultural industries is of particular interest when analysing the phenomenon of transmedia storytelling. This chapter, therefore, focuses on the songs that won a Goya award in the second decade of the century. Although it was during the first decade of the 21st century that interactive digital media began to develop as a consequence of the internet, media convergence in Spain did not consolidate to any great degree until the 2010s. Consequently, the 21st century's second decade is a key period not only for analysing transmedia storytelling through popular music in Spanish film productions, but also for assessing the extent to which Spanish cinema has matured in a context of media convergence and participatory culture.

Transmedia storytelling and popular music

Jenkins was a pioneer in theorising transmedia storytelling, a term he developed further in subsequent research³ and which has been extended from both a semiotic and narratological

perspective by researchers such as Scolari and Rodríguez-Ferrándiz⁴, among many other scholars. For Jenkins, narratives are neither a movement nor a paradigm, but rather a provocation, a concept that shows the extent to which the various sectors of the cultural industries are interconnected through different texts and platforms. There is consensus among scholars that the defining characteristic of transmedia storytelling is the convergence of cultural industries and media, and fan participation in creating discourses. The capacity of a particular content to attract users' attention, be resignified and then turned into content with the potential to spread is known as engagement⁵. Given that cinema has been closely linked to music since its origins, the initial premise is that transmedia storytelling is an ideal concept by which to examine the relationships that bring the recording industry and cinema together through a transmedia analysis of original songs written specifically for films.

Jenkins defines transmedia storytelling as a process whereby part of the fiction in a cultural product (music, cinema, novel, video game, etc.) get dispersed across multiple channels, creating a new entertainment experience that has been adapted to the features of its particular medium of delivery. According to Jenkins⁶, transmedia storytelling has three main characteristics. Firstly, the story must extend across several media, and each text must expand on the narrative world; secondly, said expansion is complemented by user-generated content or UGC, either producer-backed or fan-generated; and thirdly, the expanded narrative world is autonomous, does not depend on the “mothership” and runs through the different textual parts of which it consists. However, textual expansions of transmedia storytelling can also be characterised by a compression process⁷, such as film trailers, intended as promotion, to draw viewers in or to ensure narrative continuity. It follows, therefore, to observe whether songs expand on the film's storytelling in terms of compression.

The concept of transmedia storytelling is wide and complex, and it has been particularly effective for understanding the dynamics of super-productions and franchises such as *The*

Matrix, *Star Wars*, *Harry Potter* and *Star Trek*, the narrative worlds of which have spread across a range of texts and platforms that have created new experiences of entertainment.

However, the sample set addressed here, Spanish cinema, generally lacks strategies or budgets that are large enough for a film to be produced with a transmedia mentality.

However, and given that the concept of transmedia storytelling reveals the interconnectivity between texts, beyond the intertextuality, the characteristics of transmedia storytelling are used as the frame of reference to analyse whether original songs are capable of spreading a film's storytelling.

Although there has been little research into transmedia storytelling and music, some approaches to the phenomenon do exist that analyse both popular music and a range of cultural products in which music plays a relevant role in their transmedia expansion. One of the most significant case studies analysing transmedia strategies in popular music can be found in Jost⁸, who analysed how in 1998 the Blur frontman Damon Albarn and the illustrator Jamie Hewlett created Gorillaz, an English band whose members were fictitious cartoon characters who featured in animated shorts, music videos and video games, and performed in web-based music stories. The band's fans, in turn, played their part in enriching the stories of these characters by spreading the narrative across a range of platforms. Gorillaz connected with fans who were reluctant to buy a CD at the height of the physical format crisis. In this particular case, it was found that fan involvement directly helped to promote CD sales and reinforce the band's identity, making it much more meaningful to its fans⁹. Similarly, Vizciano-Verdú and Sánchez-Olmos¹⁰ analysed how the "Main Title" theme tune from the series *Game of Thrones* created new storytelling and aesthetic experiences as a result of fanvids¹¹ created and uploaded by fans. A similar phenomenon occurred with Disney films¹², video games¹³ and music videos¹⁴. This chapter seeks to broaden these lines of research into original songs composed for films.

Original songs matter in films

Since the second half of the 20th century, original songs composed specifically for a film have gradually become a significant part of the film industry. Kathryn Kalinak maintains that Hollywood's attraction to popular music is due to the commercial pressures that cinema faced in the middle of the last century¹⁵. Furthermore, cinema studios acquired record companies to cross-promote studios and vice versa, and pop songs became a requirement in films due to their capability not only to increase profitability but also as a commercial strategy to reach new audiences. Additionally, the exponential growth of pop music in the 1950s and 1960s demonstrated that popular songs establish meaning more directly and efficiently than background music, due to their power to trigger emotional responses.

Directors invite well-known artists to compose original songs for their film due to the fact that the audience will recognise them¹⁶, and because there is often a strong sense that the song is a sincere expression of the singer's own feelings¹⁷. Thus, the audience connect directly with artists and then with the narrative of the film. Even if the audience do not recognise the singer, they will be able to decode a particular and familiar style that gives off a similar emotion, mood and context as the famous artist¹⁸. In this regard, Hesmondhalgh highlighted the importance of songs in understanding the emotional effects, because so much of popular music revolves around songs, rather than instrumental music¹⁹. Whereas music can be more polysemic, lyrics can explicitly transmit and anchor the film's meaning. According to Kalinak²⁰, songs are composed through the language of music, which means that they fulfil similar functions as instrumental music: unity, mood, atmosphere, space and time, and emotional connection to a film. Similarly, Kovac argues that songs convey and spread not only specific meaning, but also hidden signs that suggest certain emotions that the characters

are feeling but not voicing²¹. As a composer, Kovac found that “song becomes an important addition to the script, making sure the audience gets the right message”²².

Altogether, the music, narratives and images in their respective music videos work as a kind of musical trailer that draws together the premise of the story, but also facilitates the audience’s emotional connection with the film. According to the composer Aleksandra Kovac, original songs “are significant documents, musical postcards of our culture and times, reflecting the needs and desires of the audience”²³. Kovac claims the task of writing a song is difficult because the composer needs to convey the specific mood of the film to connect the audience emotionally to the story while also ensuring that the song fits within the film’s cultural and social context. Finally, for Kovac, when an original song appears over the end credits, it represents a gentle but firm reminder that the audience will embrace reality again²⁴. In short, there seems to be both an academic and a professional consensus in recognising the importance of original songs as narrative artefacts that can perform a function that is as equally crucial as the score, and provide the film with the added value that popular music brings. The capacity of original songs to expand on a film’s narrative is analysed below.

Goya-winning films and songs

Between 2010 and 2020, the Academy awarded Goyas to original songs mainly from dramas (five out of 11), followed by comedy dramas (four out of 11) and, lastly, action films. These include two musicals: the comedy *La llamada* [*Holy Camp!*] (2017) and the social drama *Cerca de tu casa* [*At Your Doorstep*] (2016). In most cases, these were low-budget productions, as is often the case in the Spanish cinema industry. In fact, only three films, *El niño* (2014), *Palmeras en la nieve* [*Palm Trees in the Snow*] (2015) and *Campeones* [*Champions*] (2018), exceeded a budget of €4 million. Finally, there is a predominance of

independent films, leading to a more self-governed market, except in the case of the major productions indicated, which deal with more universal themes.

Regarding performers, the composer and singer Silvia Pérez Cruz stands out for having won three times, namely for “Chicuelo” in the film *Blancanieves* [*Snow White*] in 2013, for “Ai, ai, ai” in *Cerca de tu casa* in 2017, and for “Intemperie” for the film of the same name [*Out in the Open*] in 2020. Silvia Pérez Cruz is an actress and composer, and her work fuses traditional music, flamenco, *copla* and pop, making her one of the most versatile and innovative voices in Spanish music and an ideal singer for historic films depicting Spanish traditional music.

In terms of the directors’ gender, there is a characteristic lack of equality in the Goya winners. *La boda de Rosa* [*Rosa’s Wedding*] is the only film directed by a woman, Icíar Bollaín, and the only one with a feminist theme. The other films were all directed by men. Focusing on the musicians, the gender imbalance only improves in terms of the performer, namely that six of the 11 winners are songs performed by a woman. However, regarding the composers of the songs, there is even greater imbalance, as only three women, Carmen Agredano, Silvia Pérez Cruz and Rozalén, perform their own songs. As a result, the Goya awards reflect the patriarchal structure of the music industry canon by only recognising women in the role of performer, even when they are renowned composers, as is the case of Silvia Pérez Cruz, who only composed one of the winning songs. For Citron²⁵, one of the most important characteristics that adds legitimacy to the musical canon is the score, not solely because it is the main way that the canon is disseminated, but also because it grants the music a material value through the sheet music, gives composers legitimacy and turns them into authors imbued with a transcendental, timeless subjectivity. However, the fact that the musical canon has afforded greater relevance to the creation rather than the performance does not mean that the score is more valuable than the performance²⁶.

Original song placement types: Promotional and narrative

With regard to how original songs are placed within films, it can be observed that they do not always form part diegetically of the storyworld. In fact, only seven of the 11 films insert the song diegetically (*Yo, también* [*Me Too*] (2009), *Blancanieves*, *La voz dormida* [*The Sleeping Voice*] (2011), and *Cerca de tu casa*, or extra-diegetically (*Yo, también*, *La llamada*, *Campeones* and *Intemperie*). In all cases, the placement of the songs is timed to coincide with key moments of the story. Secondly, six films placed the original songs at for the end and credits (see table 14.1). In both cases, the original song serves to contextualise, reinforce the mood and anchor the story's meanings.

The selection of original songs and artists who compose and perform the Goya-winning original songs is characterised by two practices. The first and most common can be described as promotional practice, and the second relates to the film's narrative characteristics.

Promotional practice, as discussed below, performs the role of transmedia storytelling to a greater degree than songs that have been placed for purely narrative purposes. As we will see, there are song that pragmatically can be observed in both categories.

Promotional placement

The promotional category relates to the composition of original songs by famous composers and performers in the Spanish music industry, who have topped the charts and who therefore add a form of promotion to the film through the music, not just in terms of the songs, but also through music videos containing scenes from the film, and lyrics that explicitly relate to the film's storytelling. This is the case of the songs performed by Guille Milkyway, Jorge Drexler, Josh Rouse, India Martínez, Riki Rivera and David Santisteban, Pabló Alborán, Leiva, Coque Malla and Rozalén. Most films, therefore, commission famous artists from Spain's music industry to perform songs that have a promotional purpose behind them. A

variety of musical styles are represented among the winning songs, namely indie, rock, pop and flamenco pop. In all cases, the artists composed songs with lyrics that expand on the film's storytelling, but in ways that suit their own musical styles. As a result, the audience unambiguously recognise the songs' famous performers, who act as a kind of ambassador for the film. Furthermore, both the styles of the songs and their performers make the film feel familiar to the audience, establishing the mood by which it is to be interpreted.

Narrative placement

Another type of composition is observed, namely of songs that are placed diegetically and which have been adapted to the film's storytelling, as is the case with the song "Ai, ai, ai" in the musical drama *Cerca de tu casa*. This placement type is also used to transport the viewer to the point in history that the film seeks to depict, as is the case of Carmen Agredano in *La voz dormida*, and Silvia Pérez Cruz in *Blancanieves* and *Intemperie*. The songs also help to identify the geographic location depicted in the films. In other words, both the context and the part of the imaginary represented require traditional songs that are outside the logic of the kind of urban popular music that currently dominates the music industry. The three songs indicated above were composed in accordance with traditional Andalusian music conventions and contextualise a particular time in history, specifically the period following the Spanish Civil War (1940s) for *La voz dormida* and *Intemperie*, and the 1920s for *Blancanieves*. In the case of "La nana de la hierbabuena" in *La voz dormida*, the song is a lullaby, a song type that is widespread in the Spanish music tradition. The lullaby draws its inspiration from flamenco, and therefore provides both a geographic and a symbolic frame of reference for the main character, a peasant woman willing to die for her anti-fascist ideology. "Intemperie", however, is a type of *copla* with an unsettling percussion track that highlights the drama taking place in a rural Spain devastated by the post-war period. Finally, the song in

Blancanieves is a flamenco composition that contextualises, sets the mood and highlights the importance of the title character's mother, a flamenco singer. In these examples, therefore, no notable forms of transmedia spread are detected through the songs, as they do not form part of the conventional circuit of the music industry, but rather are drawn from traditional music. However, even though the songs reflect traditional Spanish music in a particular place and time, they are produced within the scope of current production logic.

Secondly, there songs only placed in the film over the end credits being part of the end of the film and helping the audience returning to reality gradually while still listening to a song that refers and recall the film's storyword.

Transmedia analysis of original songs

To determine whether the songs have the capacity to expand on the film's storytelling, and using the characteristics of transmedia storytelling set out by Jenkins (2009) identified above, the songs' lyrics are analysed to determine whether they include storytelling aspects from the film. They are then analysed to determine if there are video clips shared on video platforms and whether they have placed the original song in the clip with the intention of promoting the film. Finally, the existence of any user-generated content that uses the original songs is observed. In all cases, the expanded texts are identified as being independently made or otherwise. Table 1 shows the research sample set and the variables used to analyse the transmedia spread.

Table 14.1. Research sample set

<i>Year</i>	<i>Film</i>	<i>Song</i>	<i>Artists</i>	<i>Lyrics</i>	<i>Video clip</i>	<i>Trailer</i>	<i>UGC</i>	<i>Credits</i>
2010	<i>Yo, también</i> Álvaro Pastor, Antonio Navarro	“Yo también”	Guille Milkyway	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
2011	<i>Lope</i> De Andrucha Waddington	“Que el soneto nos tome por sorpresa”	Jorge Drexler	Yes	Yes	No	No	x
2012	<i>La voz dormida</i> Benito Zambrano	“Nana de la hierbabuena”	Carmen Agredano	Yes	No	No	No	No
2013	<i>Blancanieves</i> Pablo Berger	“No te puedo encontrar”	Silvia Pérez Cruz y Juan Gómez “Chicuelo”	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
2014	<i>La gran familia española</i> Daniel Sánchez Arévalo	“Do You Really Want to Be in Love?”	Josh Rouse	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
2015	<i>El Niño</i> Daniel Monzón	“Niño sin miedo”	India Martínez, Riki Rivera y David Santisteban	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
2016	<i>Palmeras en la nieve</i> Fernando González Molina	“Palmeras en la nieve”	Lucas Vidal y Pablo Alborán	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
2017	<i>Cerca de tu casa</i> Eduard Cortés	“Ai, ai, ai”	Silvia Pérez Cruz	Yes	No	No	No	No
2018	<i>La llamada</i> Javier De Ambrossi y Javier Calvo	“La Llamada”	Leyva	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
2019	<i>Campeones</i> Javier Fesser	“Este es el momento”	Coque Malla	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
2020	<i>Intemperie</i> Benito Zambrano	“Intemperie”	Javier Ruibal/ Silvia Pérez Cruz	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
2021	<i>La boda de Rosa</i> Icíar Bollain	“Que no, que no”	María Rozalén	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Transmedia storytelling through song lyrics

The film's storytelling spreads in all cases through the lyrics of the songs, even if the song is not placed in the film itself and only appears over the end credits. In this regard, according to Scolari²⁷, compression is one of the features of this spread, as the lyrics manage to condense the premise of the film into a song lasting less than four minutes. For example, *La boda de Rosa* is a feminist comedy that deals with the life of older women who have devoted their lives to caring for others. When the main character realises that nobody is looking out for her, she decides to make a radical change to her life, even though her family is against it. The song "Que no, que no"²⁸, composed by Rozalén, only plays over the end credits and summarises the film's premise: "*Y si no me sale del corazón, voy a aprender a decir que no, quien bien me quiere lo va a comprender, yo no nací solo pa complacer*" ["And if I don't feel it in my heart, I'm gonna learn to say no, whoever really loves me will understand, I wasn't born just to please"]. This example shows how the song reinforces the film's theme through a song, a characteristic that is observed in all the cases analysed. An argument could therefore be made for the existence of a canon in this particular practice that consists of composers condensing the premise of the story into a song, sharing the *topoi* of the film's discourse and reinforcing the discourse that is developed through the songs' lyrics. The characteristics of transmedia storytelling as identified by Jenkins (2009) are therefore met, as the songs recreate some of the most important aspects of the film, while also having an autonomous function by contributing to the story's spread through the music's intrinsic characteristics, i.e. a style that provides context, a style that provides context, sets a mood and establishes the target audience. Furthermore, by developing the discourse, famous artists help the audience to connect and identify with the film through the performers' expressive skills, as maintained by Fraile and Hesmondhalgh²⁹.

Regarding the platforms on which the stories are spread, most of the songs were released in digital format on Apple Music or Amazon, and can also be listened to on streaming platforms such as Spotify and social media sites such as YouTube. However, not all of the artists released their songs in physical format, one exception being *Palmeras en la nieve*. This super-production released a double CD that features songs inspired by the film and the award-winning song by Pablo Alborán, expanding on the film's storytelling. In this regard, this format meets the characteristics of transmedia storytelling, as not only does it lead to the story spreading across other platforms, through the music, but the CD also includes new tracks that do not appear in the film, spreading the storytelling through both the music and the lyrics. The same cannot be said of the record labels of Leiva and Josh Rose, which only released discs with the original songs, without enriching the storytelling by including other songs inspired by the film.

Music videos

Traditionally, music videos have been considered a product of the music industry aimed at promoting and selling the song. Vernallis believes that this definition may only be valid up to the emergence of the internet³⁰, given that currently modern music videos are much more complex audiovisual devices. A music video, therefore, could be an audiovisual product that the audience recognise as such. Approaching the original song music videos from a transmedia perspective, they are observed to function as an audiovisual platform that spreads the film's storytelling, as well as having a twofold promotional purpose: to publicise both the song and the film at the same time. Music videos released on YouTube help to generate engagement with both the film's audience and that of the artists themselves. To that end, music videos include original scenes from the film and allude intertextually to the film by generating another audiovisual text, one that is enriched both by the original song and by

the artists themselves, who are recognised by their fans. The exception is the theme song of *La gran familia española* [Family United], from 2014, which does not have a music video and thus fails to harness its capacity to generate engagement.

Music trailers

The films' trailers, which can be defined as processes of compression, do not include the original songs, thus failing to harness the music's capacity to expand on the storytelling, with the exception of *La llamada*, which is the only film to use the potential of the original song in the official trailer to generate engagement. In all of the other films, the trailers are conservative in their approach and use only background music to promote the film.

It is worth noting the case of the video for "Este es el momento" [*This is the Time*] by Coque Malla, which won the Goya award for the film *Campeones*³¹ in 2018. It is an example of a hybrid format that contains elements of a trailer, music video and lyric video at the same time. The video is available on the YouTube channel of the artist, Coque Malla, as a lyric video, but it also shows scenes from the film, including dialogue by the characters interspersed with the singer's performance. The result is a trailer and video hybrid that combines the capabilities of each format. As a trailer it features the most persuasive fragments of dialogue, and as a music video it generates a common thread that contextualises, sets a mood, injects new meanings through the lyrics and generates expectation in the audience, who recognise both the artist and his musical style. This audiovisual hybrid is also presented in a similar way to how the song is placed extra-diegetically in the film. In other words, "Este es el momento" plays in the film at a key moment; the song's placement is a set-up for the resolution of the narrative conflict. The song is placed as a kind of music video, lasting five minutes, showing inspiring shots and dialogue, and informing the audience that

the heroes have overcome their difficulties and are ready to face the big challenge that is to come.

User-generated content

UGC analysis reveals one of the key characteristics of transmedia storytelling that can be analysed in songs that have won Goya awards. The amount and diversity of audiovisual content produced, remixed, recreated and shared on social media by viewers indicate the capacity of songs to extend on the film's storytelling, but above all it shows how mass culture becomes popular culture when viewers imbue a particular text, in this case the film, with relevant meaning in line with their own values and identities. As Fiske maintains³², audiences produce popular culture when it engages with or gives meaning to a mass culture product in their lives.

Consequently, viewers resignify texts provided by mass culture within a context of participatory culture, giving them value and meaning, and put them back into circulation while highlighting the most relevant characteristics in their lives. It is true that some texts contain meanings that are more attractive than others to be recreated and shared³³. In the case of the songs considered here, UGC is residual and spontaneous, i.e. it involves no prior planning by the film's producers. This content consists mainly of multi-modal videos uploaded by users on YouTube and short videos shared on TikTok. Not even a super-production such as *Campeones* has a transmedia strategy that invites viewers to generate content relating to the film. In terms of formats, there are examples of lyric videos on YouTube, or shorter formats such as TikTok videos. Lyric videos are the UGC that fans most commonly share online, particularly on YouTube.

In the case of videos shared on TikTok, user-generated content is more varied and diverse.

This is due to the affordances provided by the TikTok platform itself; users provide their own

images using the original song from the film, which is available on the platform under licence by the owners of the song's copyright. It is therefore easy for users with no video editing skills to share their videos instantly, using the film's music and thus helping to spread the film's narrative premise. As a result, there are more short videos expanding on the film's storytelling in accordance with viewers' values shared on TikTok than are uploaded to YouTube. This is because, whereas creating and uploading videos to YouTube has become one of the practices of amateur users with a certain level of skills in terms of digital and audiovisual abilities, TikTok has democratised prosumption and provides an easy and spontaneous way for users to share videos featuring songs from films. On the other hand, the TikTok platform has agreements in place with music distributors for the use of songs on the app, facilitating the creation of videos that use film music without breaching any copyright restrictions. This explains why TikTok content is much more numerous and varied. The song "La llamada" has 324 videos, "Este es el momento" from *Campeones* has 16 videos, "Que no, que no" by Rozalén has 327 TikTok videos, "Palmeras en la nieve" has 115 videos, and the film *El niño* has more than a hundred TikTok videos spreading the film's storytelling. In all cases, users harness the music to help enunciate their discourse, anchor meanings and contextualise the images that they are sharing. There are also songs in the sample set which, although included in the TikTok catalogue, do not feature in any videos, as is the case with "Ai, ai, ai" and "Intemperie", confirming the hypothesis that these songs fail to leverage the promotional possibilities afforded by transmedia storytelling.

Conclusions

This research has served to provide an insight into the close relationship that exists between cinema and popular music. Analysis of the songs that won a Goya award in the second decade of the 21st century confirms that by applying a transmedia perspective, original songs

help to expand and reinforce the film's storytelling across a range of media and formats. The songs' lyrics, the style of music and the use of film footage in music videos, lyric videos and short TikTok videos all contain storytelling elements of the film that are adapted to each medium, add a level of enrichment to the film and generate audience engagement depending on their particular characteristics.

In terms of song choice, two placement practices are observed, one that is promotional and one that relates more to the film's storytelling. In terms of promotional placement, the songs are performed by famous artists from the urban pop music scene in order for the audience to identify with them, leading to the artists becoming ambassadors for the films and to the songs acting as a promotional tool for film and artist alike. In this regard, a dichotomy is observed; it becomes difficult to separate when the song is just music or is advertising, i.e. whether it is in fact musicvertising³⁴.

The songs are placed in the films in two ways: either integrated into the film's storytelling, both diegetically and extra-diegetically, or over the end credits. In the first case, it can be concluded that all the songs are inserted at key moments and meet a range of purposes as indicated by Kovac³⁵: they reinforce the film's storytelling and help to decode the discourse. They also create a mood, establish a geographic setting, contextualise the point in history, ready the audience for the denouement, anchor the meanings of the discourse and generate aesthetic pleasure. Finally, the songs function independently, even if they include a reference to the film, thus fulfilling one of the characteristics of transmedia storytelling: spreading the storytelling across other platforms, in this case through music.

However, in the films that do not place the original song into the film's storytelling, such as the Pablo Alborán song (*Palmeras en la nieve*) and the song by Rozalén (*La boda de Rosa*), the songs are placed over the end credits instead, so that the audience's return to reality is gradual, while still listening to a song that reinforces the film's premise. In this regard, these

films do not take advantage of the persuasive effects of the original song's placement in the film and miss out on the opportunity to improve the transmedia spread, i.e. the opportunity is lost to relive the storytelling experiences in a song that is outside of the film itself. One explanation for this situation may be that original songs are not always composed to emphasise the film's storytelling, but rather as a promotional product, or to fill out the creative categories for a production when it comes to being entered for the Goya awards. In any event, there seems to be greater connection and coordination, and therefore a greater identification, between film and song in productions in which the original song not only forms part of the storytelling, but is also placed to coincide with one of the key moments of the film's narrative structure. This is the case for *La llamada*, *Campeones*, *La voz dormida*, *Blancanieves*, *Intemperie* and *Cerca de tu casa*. In all these cases, not only does the song expand on the film's storytelling, it also connects the listener to the storytelling imaginary that the film represents. Conversely, when the songs only appear over the end credits, or not even at this point, as is the case of *El niño*, the songs only work as a kind of jingle for the film, thus failing to harness all their persuasive power. For this reason, and considering the fact that transmedia storytelling covers a great many perspectives, such as semiotics, economics and technology, the films' original songs are observed to have the capacity to influence the different forms of narrative, production and promotional logic of Spanish cinema, though it is also observed that they do not always make the most of these possibilities, at least not in persuasive terms.

Similarly, it is observed that whereas the film industry makes use of the storytelling and promotional possibilities brought by the composition of original songs that expand on and enrich the film's storytelling, the same does not occur with the music industry, which fails to harness these synergies that could help launch a range of music products that have an intertextual connection with the film's meaning. In fact, only Warner Music released a CD

inspired by *Palmeras en la nieve*, and in so doing succeeding in harnessing the advantages of transmedia storytelling by creating a product that includes both the original song by Pablo Alborán and other songs by related artists.

In the case of the films' trailers, it can be concluded that they do not expand on the storytelling of the films through their original songs. Only the song "La llamada" by Leiva forms part of the official trailer. Again, producers fail to harness the advantages offered by transmedia storytelling to expand on the story through the same format but with different content to generate engagement and reach an audience that identify with the artists performing the songs.

However, music videos emerge as the most effective format for spreading and enriching the film's storytelling by showing footage from the film, turning the music video into a short version of the film, one that condenses, emphasises and recalls the film's best moments and which allows the audience to recreate those emotions in less than four minutes. However, in this case and according to Scolari³⁶, rather than expanding on the storytelling, what the music video and trailer do is produce a narrative contraction. Regarding user-generated content (UGC), it can be concluded that its impact is low, scant and of little significance when compared with productions such as *Harry Potter*, *Star Wars* or *Joker*. In all cases, UGC comes about through user initiative and is more common on TikTok than on YouTube. This is due to the affordances provided by TikTok, which allows the song from the films to be placed into the video with the user's own images, and for the clip to be shared straight away. Again, producers miss out on the opportunity to release texts for users to resignify and release in relation to the film's storytelling, indicating a lack of maturity in Spanish cinema when it comes to making use of transmedia storytelling.

Finally, this research is an initial exploratory approach that applies the transmedia theory to the original songs of Spanish films that won Goya awards by applying its characteristics in a

deductive way. The results therefore differ from the analyses that Jenkins, Scolari³⁷ and other researchers have conducted in case studies that are characterised above all by a high impact on transmedia spread across various platforms and social media types. However, this research is pertinent as it focuses on the music, which has received little attention in transmedia theory terms. In this regard, it can be concluded that the original songs play a key role both in the film's storytelling and in how that storytelling is extended across other formats.

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¹ Lyric videos are music videos that focus on the lyrics of songs and which are produced and shared by users on social media platforms.

² The Oscar for Best Original Song was awarded for the first time to Con Conrad and Herb Magidson for “The Continental”, performed by Ginger Rogers in the film *The Gay Divorcee*. In Spain, the song “Fugitivas”, by Manuel Malou, Natboccara and Chaleco, won the first Goya award for the film *Fugitivas* by Miguel Hermoso.

³ Henry Jenkins, *Convergence Culture. Where Old and New Media Collide*. (New York & London: New York University Press, 2006).

Jenkins, Henry. 2009. “The Revenge of the Origami Unicorn: Seven Principles of Transmedia Storytelling”. *Confessions of an Aca-Fan* (20 August, 2015).

⁴ Carlos Scolari, *Narrativas transmedia: cuando todos los medios cuentan* (Barcelona: Deusto, 2013). EPUB. Raúl Rodríguez-Ferrándiz, “Transmedia. By Any Media Necessary”, in *Reimagining Communication: Action*, ed. Michael Filimowicz and Veronika Tzankova (New York & London: Routledge, 2015).

⁵ Henry Jenkins, Sam Ford, and Joshua Green, *Spreadable Media: Creating Value and Meaning in a Networked Culture* (New York: New York University Press, 2013).

⁶ Jenkins, Henry. 2009. “The Revenge of the Origami Unicorn: Seven Principles of Transmedia Storytelling”. *Confessions of an Aca-Fan*, 20 August 2015.

⁷ Carlos Scolari, *Narrativas transmedia*, 243, EPUB.

⁸ Cristófer Jost, “Popular Music and Transmedia Aesthetics: On the Conceptual Relation of Sound, Audio-Vision and Live Performance”, in *Reinventing Sound: Music and Audiovisual Culture*, ed. Enrique Encabo. (Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2015), 2–13.

⁹ Alex Jeffery. “Marketing and materiality in the popular music transmedia of Gorillaz’ Plastic Beach”, *Mediterranean Journal of Communication*, no. 8 (2), (2017), 67–80.

¹⁰ Arantza Vizcaíno-Verdú and Cande Sánchez-Olmos, “La música y las narraciones transmedia: estudio de caso del ‘Main Title’ de la serie Juego de Tronos”, in *Más allá de la pantalla. Música, sonido e imagen*, ed. Enrique Encabo (Sabadell: Elpoblet Ediciones 2018), 169–204.

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- ¹¹ A fanvid is a type of music video created and spread by fans recreating a film or television series, and is usually set to music.
- ¹² Arantxa Vizcaíno-Verdú, Ignacio Aguaded, and Paloma Contreras-Pulido, “Understanding Transmedia Music on YouTube through Disney Storytelling”, *Sustainability*, no.13(7), (2021), 3667.
- ¹³ Pau Riera, “Narrativa, música y transmedia en Nier: hacia una nueva obra de arte total”. *Caracteres. Estudios culturales y críticos de la esfera digital*, 2(1), (2013),169–186.
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- ¹⁴ Toni Roig, Toni and Gemma San Cornelio, “Prácticas de cocreación en vídeos musicales: el caso de Evolution of Get Lucky”. *Anàlisi. Quaderns de Comunicació i Cultura*, no. 51 (2014), 49–63.
- ¹⁵ Kathryn Kalinak, *Film Music: A Very Short Introduction* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2010), 85.
- ¹⁶ Teresa Fraile Prieto, “La música en el cine español hoy. Nuevos protagonistas y sistemas de producción”. *Trípodos*, no. 26 (2010), 67–80.
- ¹⁷ David Hesmondhalgh, *Why Music Matters*, (Chichester Malden: Wiley-Blackwell, 2013), 23.
- ¹⁸ Teresa Fraile Prieto, “La música en el cine español hoy”, 69.
- Aleksandra Kovac, “Musical Postcards of Our Time: A Personal Look at the Importance of Original Pop Songs Written for Mainstream Films”, *New Sound: International Journal of Music*, no. 45(1) (2015), 83–93.
- ¹⁹ David Hesmondhalgh, *Why Music Matters*, 23.
- ²⁰ Kathryn Kalinak, *Film Music*, 86.
- ²¹ Aleksandra Kovac, “Musical Postcards of Our Time”, 87
- ²² Aleksandra Kovac, “Musical Postcards of Our Time”, 87.
- ²³ Aleksandra Kovac, “Musical Postcards of Our Time”, 87.
- ²⁴ Aleksandra Kovac, “Musical Postcards of Our Time”, 85.
- ²⁵ Marcia Citron, *Gender and the Musical Canon* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1993).
- ²⁶ Laura Viñuela, *La perspectiva de género y la música popular: dos nuevos retos para la musicología*. (Oviedo: KRK Ediciones, 2003), 37.
- ²⁷ Carlos Scolari, *Narrativas transmedia*.
- ²⁸ The song can be heard at Rozalén [username], “Rozalén, La Sonora Santanera - Que no, que no”, 10 July 2020, YouTube video, URL: <https://youtu.be/CsnTVgXFOn8>
- ²⁹ David Hesmondhalgh, *Why Music Matters*, 23.
- Teresa Fraile Prieto, “La música en el cine español hoy”, 69.
- ³⁰ Carol Vernallis, *Unruly Media: YouTube, Music Video, and the New Digital Cinema*. (New York: Oxford University Press, 2013), 208.
- ³¹ The song can be heard on Coque Malla [username], “Coque Malla - Este es el momento (Tema Original de la película Campeones)”, 6 April 2018, YouTube video, URL: <https://youtu.be/rr79KgMnICY>
- ³² John Fiske, *Understanding Popular Culture*. (London: Routledge, 1989), 126.
- ³³ John Fiske, *Understanding Popular Culture*, 120–126.
- ³⁴ Sánchez-Olmos, Cande. 2018. “Musicvertising in branded music content. An analysis of formats, features and sectors”. *Mediterranean Journal of Communication*, no. 9 (1), (2018), 305–319.
- ³⁵ Aleksandra Kovac, “Musical Postcards of Our Time”, 83–93.
- ³⁶ Carlos Scolari, *Narrativas transmedia*.
- ³⁷ Henry Jenkins, *Convergence Culture*.
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